

1 **Are olfactory stimuli able to induce emotional responses in a positive context?**

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9 **Abstract**

10 The perception of olfactory stimuli can influence animal emotions and behaviors, which
11 are critical for survival and adaptation. This study explored the emotional valences of
12 three olfactory stimuli—orange essential oil, wolf feces, and cadaverine—in sheep,
13 tested in a non-stressful environment enriched with social and food resources.
14 Contrary to expectations, wolf feces, while repellent, did not trigger overt stress
15 behaviors such as increased vocalizations or agitation. Similarly, orange essential oil
16 did not elicit strong positive valence responses, suggesting that the positive
17 experimental context may mask its effect. Interestingly, cadaverine, typically
18 associated with body decomposition, induced emetic responses in two individuals,
19 indicating potential disgust. Overall, this research highlights the complex interplay
20 between social, food, and environmental factors in shaping the emotional responses
21 of sheep to olfactory stimuli, underscoring the importance of context and individual
22 variability. These findings contribute to a better understanding of olfactory influences
23 on animal welfare and behavior.

24 **Keywords:** Sheep, Cues, Predator, Odor, Welfare

25 **Highlights**

- 26 • Olfactory stimuli were tested in a positive context combining social and food
27 resources.
- 28 • Wolf feces exhibited a clear repellent effect but did not trigger stress
29 behaviors.
- 30 • Orange essential oil did not elicit strong positive emotional responses in this
31 context.
- 32 • Cadaverine caused emetic responses in some individuals, suggesting
33 potential disgust.
- 34 • Importance of considering context and personality in the study of olfactory-
35 driven behaviors

37 **Implications**

38 This study investigates the ability of odors to induce emotion in sheep. Emotion-related
39 behaviors were measured in adult sheep exposed to different olfactory stimuli (orange
40 essential oil, wolf feces, and cadaverine), in the presence of congeners and food
41 (positive context). Our results challenge the emotional valences of olfactory stimuli,
42 reinforcing the idea that animal behaviors result from a trade-off between social and
43 food motivations. Overall, these findings contribute to the comprehension of the
44 efficacy of olfactory stimuli in animal welfare and behavior. Specifically, our results
45 highlight the importance of considering personality traits and the context in which the
46 study is conducted to reduce stress.

47

48

49 **Introduction**

50 In sheep, olfactory cues are essential for assessing, perceiving and understanding
51 their environment and the world around them. Soon after birth, olfaction participates in
52 the establishment of the mother-young relationship (Nowak et al. 2011), plays a role in
53 the discrimination of age-mate congeners (Ligout et al. 2004) and is involved in the
54 development of food preferences (Provenza et al. 1992; Simitzis et al. 2008). In
55 addition, it seems that sheep express spontaneous attraction and preference for food
56 odorized with orange essential oil (Simitzis et al. 2005, 2008). These examples show
57 how olfaction allows animals to express a preference for a social or food object,
58 demonstrating that olfactory stimuli can be attractive and have a positive valence
59 (Nielsen et al. 2015). That the place of olfaction in strategies for avoidance of certain
60 poisonous plants or contaminated feces is not so evident, questioning the affective and
61 cognitive mechanisms involved in food selection (Provenza et al. 1992) and
62 mechanisms of parasitism avoidance (Cooper et al. 2000). In this latter case, the
63 foraging decisions of sheep are determined by both their physiological state, including
64 their motivation to eat, and their management of trade-offs between nutrition and
65 parasitism (Hutchings et al. 2000). In pasture, sheep also face predation; olfactory
66 information from a predator is one alarm signals used by prey trigger avoidance
67 behavior. Demonstrations of the repellent effect of the odor of a predator on sheep
68 have been reported in adult ovariectomized ewes (Ile-de-France) submitted to a
69 choice-test after a period of starvation (16h: Arnould and Signoret 1993; 20h: Arnould
70 et al. 1998). In both studies, repellent effects of predatory feces were observed (dog:
71 Arnould and Signoret 1993; wolf: Arnould et al. 1998), with a long-lasting effect of dog
72 feces (Arnould and Signoret 1993). Similar effects have been found in sheep exposed
73 to other predatory odors (tiger, lion, leopard in small tail, Wang et al. 2023; fox, wild

74 boar in Corriedale sheep, Zambra et al. 2021). This demonstrates the repulsive or
75 aversive effect of predatory odors that confers them a negative valence (Nielsen et al.
76 2015). Even if the literature suggests the existence of positive (attractive) and negative
77 (aversive or repulsive) valences of odors, the question of their ability for inducing
78 emotion remains.

79 According to appraisal theory, emotion, which is short-lived, is induced by a specific
80 event and modulated by internal and external factors (Boissy et al. 2007). However,
81 certain internal and external factors could potentially produce an emotion even without
82 a specific event and/or modulate the emotional response to a specific event. It is
83 therefore necessary to control and standardize these factors, and to measure emotion-
84 related behaviors, in order to truly demonstrate that the odor induced the emotion and
85 not simply these other factors. In this context, it is common to include a pre-experiment
86 period in the aim to habituate the individuals (Arnould and Signoret 1993, Simitzis et
87 al 2005) and, therefore, to avoid stress induced by the experimental setup (novel
88 environment, interaction with human, etc.). However, several protocols propose to
89 starve the animals in the aim to ensure feeding motivation (Arnould and Signoret 1993,
90 Arnould et al. 1998), to test them in social isolation (Arnould and Signoret 1993,
91 Arnould et al. 1998, Wang et al. 2023), or to use constraining equipment to ensure that
92 the animal smells the odor (Zambra et al. 2021). All these practices are likely to induce
93 confounding stressful effects. Some studies tested animals in the presence of
94 companion animals, but, in this case, it was necessary to diffuse the odor only to the
95 experimental animal by using a mask (Zambra et al. 2021), a fitted trough (Wang et al.
96 2023) or box (Achin et al. 2025).

97 To investigate the emotional valence of odors, we exposed individuals to olfactory
98 stimuli (OS). However, through a habituation period and, importantly, access to social

99 companions and food we ensured a positive experimental context lacking in
100 confounding factors. Emotion-related behaviors such as vocalization, agitation,
101 exploration, social contact, and food intake were analyzed to infer emotion. (Achin et
102 al. 2025). In a first experiment, we aim to explore the existence of positive and negative
103 emotional valences of OS. We chose two odors thought to have attractive (orange
104 essential oil) and repellent (wolf feces) effects, and hypothesize that these odors could
105 also have emotional valences. We expect that wolf feces will trigger negative emotion-
106 related behaviors characterized by an increased number of vocalizations, agitation,
107 seeking the proximity of congeners, and a reduction in food intake. Conversely, we
108 expect that orange essential oil will elicit positive emotion-related behaviors
109 characterized by a low number of vocalizations, increased feeding behavior, and a
110 tendency to seek proximity to the odor source. In a second experiment, we aim to
111 explore the existence of a gradation in the negative emotional valence of odors. To
112 test our hypothesis, we chose wolf feces and cadaverine, a molecule associated with
113 body decomposition. We expect that both the wolf feces and cadaverine will trigger
114 different negative emotion-related reactions, despite the non-stressful experimental
115 setup with social and food resources. This negative response is expected to manifest
116 as increased vocalization and agitation, reflected in a higher number of zones crossed,
117 accompanied with a reduction in food intake.

118

119 **Material and methods**

120 ***Animals***

121 Thirty adult ewes (Ile-de-France breed, 5-8 years old, 77.45 ± 8.12 kg) were raised in
122 the same conditions at the experimental farm UEPAO (unité expérimentale de
123 Physiologie animale de l'Orfrasière, INRAE, Nouzilly,

124 doi:10.15454/1.5573896321728955E12). One week prior the experimentation, they
125 were split into 3 groups of 10 ewes based on the randomization criteria: birth weight,
126 date of birth and last recorded weight. In addition, 4 companion adult ewes (Ile-de-
127 France breed, 7-9 years old, UEPAO), housed separately close to the experimental
128 room, participated. During the experimental period, the animals were housed in the
129 experimental building on straw and received unlimited hay and a ration of pellets to
130 cover their maintenance requirements for adults (300 g). The experiment was
131 conducted in January and February 2023, indoors. We ensured that the temperature
132 remained stable throughout the entire duration of the study.

133

134 Based on the Strange framework (Webster et Rutz 2020), the population of the
135 30 unrelated adult ewes is homogeneous in terms of age (aged between 5 and 8 years
136 old), breed (Ile-de-France breed) and rearing history. All females were raised with
137 maternal nursing under the same housing conditions, and all had given birth at least
138 once with nursing. The order in which the animals were tested was determined based
139 on their motivation. We respected this order to avoid any stress related to handling.
140 The animals were tested in the same order during each experiment, in respect of their
141 trappability and/or personality.

142

143 ***Olfactory stimuli preparation***

144 **Identification of positive and negative emotional valences of OS**

145 Two distinct OS were used: wolf feces, thought to induce negative emotion and orange
146 essential oil (*Citrus Sinensis*), thought to induce positive emotion. The wolf feces were
147 collected from three different individuals (varying in age and sex) at the ZooParc de
148 Beauval 1 week before the experimentation. To minimize the potential influence of

149 individual signatures, we mixed feces in equal proportions from each individual,
150 aliquoted in portions of 3 g and stored at -20°C. On the day of the experiment, each
151 aliquoted part was thawed and raised to room temperature before being placed on a
152 cotton pad. Orange essential oil (Sweet Orange Organic, Florihana, France) has been
153 reported to have an appetizing effect on ewes (Simitzis et al. 2005). This orange
154 essential oil contains 96% limonene, a molecule known for its calming ability as well
155 (Zhang et al. 2019). Prior to the test, 15 µl of orange essential oil was applied to the
156 cotton pad. To avoid the transfer of OS during the test, the preparation of the cotton
157 pads impregnated with the OS was carried out by a person who was never in contact
158 with animals, in a separate room annexed to the experimental building. The pads were
159 placed in a closed freezer bag before being transported to the test room and placed in
160 the box. The cotton pad was changed every 30 minutes for a same OS. Three identical
161 boxes were used, one for each OS (wolf feces, orange essential oil and water).

162 **Identification of a gradation in the negative valences of OS**

163 Two distinct OS were used: wolf feces and cadaverine. This latter is a compound found
164 in decomposed corpses and often named as the “death-associated odor” (Hussain et
165 al. 2013, Dieris et al. 2017). Some studies reported freezing or avoidance behaviors in
166 rats (Pinel, Gorzalka, et al. 1981) and zebrafish (Hussain et al. 2013) exposed to
167 cadaverine. In our study, ewes were exposed to cadaverine applied on a cotton pad
168 (1ml; Sigma analytical standard 100%). The preparation of wolf feces was similar to
169 that of the first experiment. However, we decided to increase the quantity of feces (15
170 g) with the hypothesis that this quantity could induce stronger negative emotion-related
171 behaviors. The same procedures as in the first experiment were followed to prepare
172 and transport the OS into the boxes.

173

174 **Evaluation of emotion-related behaviors induced by OS**

175 To investigate the emotional valences of the OS, individuals were exposed to an
176 experimental setup after a period of habituation, in the presence of social and food
177 resources, ensuring a positive context (Achin et al. 2025). The OS exposure lasted for
178 5 min, in the presence of 4 companions and 300g of pellets placed in a transparent
179 polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) box (Figure 1).

180
181 **Fig. 1.** Photograph of the experimental setup. Ewe 6 is being tested in the corridor.
182 Three zones were virtually delineated: on the right side the “food zone” close to the
183 food resource (300 g of pellets in green plastic bucket placed in the PMMA box), on
184 the left the “social zone” close to the companions’ pen, and in the middle the “entrance
185 zone”. During the test, the OS or cotton pad was placed behind the green bucket in the
186 box (arrow).
187

188 **Habituation**

189 For five days, the ewes were habituated to the experimental setup. During the first two
190 days, they were accustomed to the presence of the experimenters; on the third day,
191 they were habituated in groups of 3 to 4 ewes with the corridor-test. During the last two
192 days, each ewe was individually placed in the corridor-test in the presence of social
193 and food resources, and exposed to a water impregnated cotton pad (Figure 1). By the
194 end of the habituation period, we expected a decrease in the number of vocalizations,
195 as well as an increase in time spent with their heads inside the box. We presented
196 water multiple times as a neutral OS (control situation) during the tests, allowing us to

197 evaluate the response to the cotton odor while ensuring that the animals maintained
198 consistent behavioral responses throughout the study.

199 **Identification of positive and negative emotional valences of OS**

200 Here, we aimed to compare OS that are thought to have a positive (orange essential
201 oil), a negative (wolf feces) or a control situation (1.5 mL of demineralized water). The
202 order of OS presentation was randomized according to the OS, the day, and the time.
203 Each individual was exposed to a single OS per day (days 2 and 3) and to the control
204 situation (days 1 and 4). Thus, 15 animals were first exposed to orange essential oil
205 (15 μ L) and then to wolf feces (3 g). The remaining 15 animals were initially exposed
206 to wolf feces and then to orange essential oil (Table 1).

207 **Identification of a gradation in the negative valences of OS**

208 Here, we aimed to compare OS that are thought to have strong negative valences (wolf
209 feces, 15 g, and cadaverine, 1 mL), and a control situation (1.5 mL of demineralized
210 water). The order of OS presentation was randomized according to the OS, the day,
211 and the time (Table 2). Each individual was exposed to a single OS per day (days 2, 3
212 and 4) and to the control situation (day 1 and day 2, 3 or 4). Thus, 12 animals were
213 first exposed to wolf feces (15 g), followed by control situation, and then cadaverine
214 (1 mL). Nine animals were first exposed to cadaverine, followed by 15 g of wolf feces,
215 and then control situation. Finally, the last 9 ewes were first exposed to control
216 situation, followed by cadaverine, and then wolf feces (Figure 2B). The two
217 experiments were carried out two weeks apart.

218 **Behavioral measurements**

219 During the test, animals were continuously recorded by two cameras: a video
220 surveillance camera (AXIS M3025) fixed to the ceiling and a digital camera (SONY
221 HDR-CX240E camera) placed facing the PMMA box in front of the animal's face

222 (Figure 1). The videos were analyzed with Boris V.8.27.1 software (Friard et Gamba
223 2016) to extract the variables described in Table 3.

224 In addition to the behaviors analyzed using the BORIS, we also recorded the quantity
225 of pellets ingested during the 5-minute test (Food_intake). Several other behavioral
226 variables were calculated: the total time spent eating (Eat_Total_TS) was obtained by
227 summing the time spent eating in both the box and in the trough, as well as the total
228 number of eating occurrences (Eat_Total_Occ). The time spent in the box without
229 eating (Box_Head_No_Eat_TS) was calculated by subtracting the eating time from the
230 total time spent in the box. The time spent in the food resource zone without eating
231 (Food_Zone_No_Eat_TS) was determined by subtracting the eating time from the total
232 time spent in that zone. Additionally, vocalizations were analyzed by calculating their
233 distribution during five minutes.

234 ***Data analysis***

235 All statistical analyses were conducted in R (V.4.3.2; R Core team 2024). The analyses
236 were performed independently for each experiment. The animals that did not eat during
237 any of the three situations (each OS and control situation), for either experiment, were
238 excluded. Additionally, for Experiment 1, two ewes with missing values were excluded
239 from the analysis.

240 A principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to the full set of variables (29),
241 including 28 ewes for the first and 30 for the second experiments, obtained from the
242 four-control situation to examine the consistency of the behaviors of the animals
243 throughout the study, especially between the experiments (Tables 1 and 2).

244 Linear discriminant analyses (LDA) were performed with all variables (package MASS)
245 measured in animals exposed to the OS and to control situation. To identify the
246 emotional valences of the OS, LDA was performed on all variables measured in 23

247 animals in control situation (water exposure the day 1 of the first experimentation) and
248 in presence of wolf feces (3 g) and orange essential oil (15 μ L). To identify a gradient
249 in the negative valences of OS, LDA was performed on all variables in 29 animals
250 measured in control situation (water exposure the day 1 of the second
251 experimentation) and in presence of wolf feces (15 g) and cadaverine (1 mL). For both
252 analyses, the variables that were found to be discriminative (threshold = 0.75) were
253 each subjected to a Friedman test. When significant differences were detected
254 ($p < 0.05$), Bonferroni corrected post-hoc Wilcoxon tests were conducted to identify
255 specific contrasts between the situations (each OS and control situation).

256 **Results**

257 At the end of the habituation period, 23/28 animals had eaten the pellets in the PMMA
258 box (0C, 2C, 3B, 8A, 9A, Figure 2). Animals that did not eat were observed to spend a
259 lot of time close to companions and to vocalize very rarely (0 to a maximum of 6 times).
260 In contrast, several animals vocalized when they entered the experimental setup (e.g.
261 0A, 2B, 3A, 5B, 6A, 6B, 9C, Figure 2). However, in most cases, vocalizations were
262 emitted when the test was well underway, and the animals had already eaten (e.g. 5B,
263 6A, 9C). After the phase of habituation, the animals no longer expressed negative
264 emotional behaviors such as agitation or continuous vocalizations. However, we
265 noticed that the five animals that did not eat at the end of habituation did not eat during
266 exposure to the OS in the first experiment. They were therefore excluded from the
267 analyses performed to identify the valences of the OS. Before the second experiment,
268 two weeks after the first experiment, only one animal did not eat any pellet in the set
269 up. It was therefore excluded from the second analysis performed to compare the
270 negative valences of the OS.

271 **Fig. 2.** Individual profiles (N=28) during Exp1 of behaviors indicating a main interest
 272 for food resource (eat, in blue) or for social resource (located in the zone near
 273 companions, in purple) and an emotion-related behavior (vocalization, red dot). Based
 274 on these behaviors, individuals were classified in three different classes of interest:
 275 social, food and ambivalent. Star indicates the animals which ate their entire pellets
 276 ration.

277 To investigate the consistency of behavioral responses throughout the study, we
 278 examined the distribution of individuals by a PCA performed on the behaviors
 279 measured in presence of control situation (reproduced four times, Tables 1 and 2). The
 280 PCA result shows that the behavior of all individuals was consistent during each of the
 281 control tests, with an overlapping of the 4 days of water exposure, except for the 5

282 individuals who did not eat in the PMMA box at the end of the habituation period (0C,
283 2C, 3B, 8A, and 9A, Figure 3).

284 **Fig. 3.** Individuals factor map of the PCA performed with all behaviors measured in
285 control situation (Exp1: n=28 ewes and Exp2: n=30 subjected four times to control
286 situation, water; 29 variables for calculating the components). Each water exposure is
287 symbolized by different colors.

288 Finally, the PCA revealed the consistency of behavioral responses between the four
289 exposures to water. Thus, we decided to study the emotional valence of the OS by
290 comparing their behavioral impacts with those of water-exposure measured during the
291 first day of each experiment (Tables 1 and 2). This choice was motivated to minimize
292 any influence from the order of OS presentation on subsequent measures done in
293 control situations after OS exposures.

294

295

296 ***Identification of emotional positive and negative valences of OS***

297 Examination of the distribution of time spent eating and in the zone near the
298 companions, and the vocalizations during the control situation of the first day of the
299 first experimentation allows to identify different groups of individuals (Figure 2). One
300 group, consisting of five ewes, was characterized by high motivation for the social
301 resource (0C, 2C, 3B, 8A, 9A). They never ate and spent most of their time close to
302 the companions, and three of them never vocalized. The other group was
303 characterized by high motivation for the food resource. This group included the majority
304 of the ewes that ate without visiting their companions for a total cumulative time of at
305 least 50 seconds. In this group, we noticed that 3 ewes never vocalized (4A, 7A and
306 9B) and that 8 emitted the majority of their vocalizations after eating. Six of these 8 ate
307 the entire pellets ration (0A, 1B, 6A, 6B, 7B, and 9C). A third group was characterized
308 by ambivalent interest for food and social resources. There were 9 animals that ate
309 pellets but also interrupted their feeding to visit the companions at least once. Five of
310 them ate their entire pellets ration (2A, 3C, 4B, 5B, and 8B) and 6 of the 9 vocalized
311 very rarely (0 to 3 vocalizations when ewes were exposed to water; 2A, 3C, 4B, 5A,
312 6C, and 8B).

313

314 The LDA result was characterized by a first axis (LD1) that explained 65% of the
315 variance and a second axis (LD2) accounting for 35% of the variance (Figure 4A).
316 Twelve variables contributed to the LD1, LD2 or the both axis (Figure 4B).

317
 318 **Fig. 4.** Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) result. **A.** Score plot where ellipses indicate
 319 95% confidence interval of each exposure. **B.** Biplot of the variables that were found
 320 to be discriminative (threshold = 0.75) (LDA performed on 23 ewes and 29 variables,
 321 see supplementary data Table S1 for variables' contribution).

322 The Friedman analysis, performed on the different contributive variables, revealed
 323 significant effects of OS exposures on all variables except the time spent with the head
 324 in the box (Box_Head_TS), the number of occurrences in the social or entrance zones
 325 (Social_Zone_Occ and Zone_Entrance_Occ, respectively) (Table 4, see
 326 supplementary data Figure S1 for histograms). The post-hoc comparisons revealed
 327 significant differences between wolf feces exposure and the control situation. Indeed,
 328 in presence of wolf feces, the ewes ate less pellets (291 [208-297] g), were less often
 329 in the food zone (5 [3-6] s), especially when they did not eat (32.5 [23.3-41.6] s, spent
 330 in the food zone without eating), In addition, they were less often seen with their head
 331 in the PMMA box without eating (8.2 [5.1-14.5] s) and with their muzzle in contact with
 332 the walls of the PMMA box (1 [0-2.5] s). In presence of orange essential oil, the
 333 behaviors were very similar to those measured in control situation, except for the time
 334 spent in the social zone, which was higher (98 [80.1-115] s) than that measured in
 335 presence of control situation (77.2 [57.8-97.4] s). However, significant differences
 336 between orange essential oil and wolf feces exposures. First, the quantity of ingested
 337 pellets was higher in presence of orange essential oil (299.8 [297-299.8] g) than in
 338 presence of wolf feces (291 [208- 297] g). This difference is associated with higher

339 time spent eating when ewes were exposed to wolf feces (124.3 [91.5-157] s) than
340 when they were exposed to orange essential oil (100.4 [92.1-128.8] s), but with
341 opposite time spent to eat in the trough (115.2 [75.3-149.5] s with wolf feces vs
342 87.1 [70-106.6] s with orange essential oil). Altogether these results suggest that ewes
343 ate their entire pellets ration faster in presence of orange essential oil than in presence
344 of wolf feces.

345 Examination of individual profiles (Figure 2) revealed that 6/14 animals motivated by
346 food resource ate their entire pellets ration in control situation; whereas, only 2/14 ate
347 their entire ration when exposed to wolf feces. Similarly, for the ambivalent group 5/9
348 animals ate their entire ration in control situation; whereas, only one did so when
349 exposed to wolf feces. In this group, 6/9 ewes finished their entire ration when they
350 were exposed to orange essential oil. Among these 6 ewes, we noticed that 2 animals
351 ate their entire pellets ration when they were exposed to orange essential oil, even
352 though they did not do so in the presence of wolf feces or in the control situation.
353 Finally, 2 animals were observed vocalizing in control situation and in presence of wolf
354 feces, that did not do so in presence of orange essential oil (9A, 9B).

355 ***Identification of a gradient in the negative valences of OS***

356 The LDA result was characterized by a first axis (LD1) that explained 93% of the
357 variance and a second axis (LD2) accounting 7% of the variance (Figure 5A). Five
358 variables contributed to the LD1 axis (Figure 5B).

359

360
 361 **Fig. 5. A.** Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) result. **A.** Score plot where ellipses
 362 indicate 95% confidence interval of each exposure. **B.** Biplot of the variables that were
 363 found to be discriminative (threshold = 0.75) (LDA performed on 29 ewes and
 364 29 variables, see supplementary data Table S2 for variables' contribution).

365 The Friedman analyses revealed significant differences between OS exposures only
 366 for the time spent with the muzzle against the walls of the PMMA box and the latency
 367 to enter the food zone. For both variables, post-hoc comparisons revealed significant
 368 differences between wolf feces exposure and the control situation (Table 5, Figure 6).
 369 In addition, we noticed that individuals ate less pellets when they were exposed to wolf
 370 feces (294 [225-299.8] g) in comparison with cadaverine exposure (299.8 [299.8-
 371 299.8] g) or control situation (299.8 [296- 299.8] g) (Figure 6). An additive Friedman
 372 analysis revealed a overall significant effect of the OS exposure ($\chi^2 = 10.3$, $df = 2$,
 373 $p = 0.005$), the difference between wolf exposure and control situation were also
 374 significant ($p = 0.009$). Moreover, two individuals expressed emetic behaviors (2C, 9B)
 375 when they exposed to the cadaverine.

376

377 **Fig. 6.** Comparison of discriminant behaviors across Water (blue), Cadaverine
 378 (purple), and Wolf Feces (red). **A.** Time spent with the muzzle in the box. **B.** Number
 379 of occurrences of eating from the trough. **C.** Time spent the first time in the zone near
 380 the food resource. **D.** Latency to enter the zone near the food resource. **E.** Occurrence
 381 of entering the zone near the entrance. **F.** Food intake. A p-value below 0.05 is
 382 indicated by one asterisk (*). If a p-value is below 0.01, it is indicated by two asterisks
 383 (**). If a p-value is below 0.001, it is indicated by three asterisks (***)

384 **Discussion**

385 The aim of our study was to investigate the emotional valences of odors in a positive
386 context. The first experiment aimed to identify the emotional valences of orange and
387 predator feces supposed to have, respectively, a positive and a negative emotional
388 valence according to their attractive (orange, (Simitzis et al. 2005)) and repellent
389 effects (wolf, (Arnould et Signoret 1993)). While our results confirmed the repellent
390 effect of wolf feces (Arnould et Signoret 1993), we cannot conclude that it lead to a
391 strong negative emotional valence. The repellent effect of wolf feces was confirmed by
392 changed in feeding behaviors and with less proximity with the odor source (food zone
393 and head in the box when animals do not eat). However, the animals did not express
394 more emotion-related behaviors such as vocalizations, agitation or searching
395 companions when they were exposed to wolf feces compared to the control situation.
396 In the same manner, our results did not reveal any emotional valence of orange.
397 However, the difference between orange essential oil and wolf feces than between
398 orange essential oil and control situation. The lack of differences between orange
399 essential oil and control situations is probably due to the positive context we were able
400 to create with our experimental setup (Achin et al. 2025) and it should also be noted
401 that the attractive effect of orange was only observed in sheep and lambs subjected to
402 a choice test (Simitzis et al. 2005; Simitzis et al. 2008). Moreover, our study highlighted
403 different individual profiles that react differently to the orange and predator.

404 The second experiment aimed to explore the existence of a gradient of negative
405 valences among different odors thought to be stressful (cadaverine and predator).
406 Whereas our results confirmed once again the repellent effect of wolf feces, they did
407 not reveal an emotional valence of it even with an increased quantity of feces (15 g in
408 the second experimentation vs 3 g in the first one). Again, we did not observe negative

409 emotion-related behaviors such as increased number of vocalizations, increased
410 agitation or increased seeking contact with companions in presence of wolf feces in
411 comparison with the control situation. Surprisingly, we did not observe an impact of
412 cadaverine, which is named “death-associated odor” (Hussain et al. 2013, Dieris et al.
413 2017), except for two ewes that exhibited emetic behaviors in response to it, indicating
414 an emotional valence of disgust. This finding aligns with evidence suggesting that the
415 effects of cadaverine are not always aversive; for instance, it has been reported to be
416 attractive to rats in certain contexts (Heale et al., 1996). Additionally, the attractiveness
417 or repulsiveness of death-associated odors depend on the prey-predator status of the
418 species: such odors tend to be attractive to predators but repulsive to prey (Arshamian
419 et al., 2017).

420 Both experiments confirmed the repellent effect of wolf feces. Interestingly, regardless
421 of the quantity of wolf feces, ewes consistently reduced their food intake in its
422 presence. This suggests a form of avoidance behavior, confirmed by the fact that
423 animals appeared to minimize their exposure to the odor by eating more directly from
424 the through, and by spending less time exposed to the odor without eating. Conversely,
425 no such avoidance was observed for the orange odor, which ewes did not appear to
426 repel, and in some cases, they even seemed to be attracted to it.

427 An inter-individual variability in behavioral responses was observed in both
428 experiments. In presence of wolf feces, this is reflected by the different interests, for
429 food, social or both, expressed by the animals in control situation (first
430 experimentation), and the wide distributions of such variables observed in both
431 experimentations (time spent the head in the box, in social and food zones, and food
432 intake). While some ewes displayed behaviors indicative of stronger avoidance or
433 disgust, others appeared less affected, highlighting the importance of considering the

434 motivation of the animals for the olfactory stimuli (Nielsen et al. 2015) and more
435 generally the individuals' personality and experience (Webster et Rutz 2020). Indeed,
436 several studies demonstrated that animals selected odorized-food when they have
437 been previously exposed to the odor (Provenza et al. 1992, Saint-Dizier, Lévy, et
438 Ferreira 2007).

439 In addition to the importance of individual personality in shaping responses to odors,
440 our study raises the question of the context in which animals are tested. As previously
441 reported (Achin et al 2025), our experimental setup allowed to test the individuals in a
442 positive context. In this context, results described in this study, in presence of predator
443 feces, are consistent with previous reported data obtained in choice-test designs
444 (Arnould et Signoret, 1993, 1998). For example, predator feces consistently reduced
445 food intake, aligning with findings from studies in sheep (Arnould et Signoret, 1993;
446 Wang et al., 2023; Zambra et al., 2021). which was not the case in our study, as no
447 agitation was observed. These behaviors may also reflect an interaction between the
448 presence of the mask used for presenting the odors and the animal's inability to avoid
449 them. Additionally, even though the animals are not alone during the test, they cannot
450 come into direct contact with the social resource (Wang et al., 2023; Zambra et al.,
451 2021), which may exacerbate such responses, as may be the case in our experimental
452 setup.

453 Interestingly, while many studies focus on behavioral modifications, few have directly
454 examined the number of vocalizations as an indicator of stress (Arnould and Signoret,
455 1993; Wang et al., 2023; Zambra et al., 2021), which is precisely what we have done
456 in our study. This is particularly noteworthy given that vocalizations are widely regarded
457 as one of the most robust stress indicators in sheep (Baldock et Sibly 1990; Lyons,
458 Price, et Moberg 1993; Guesdon et al. 2012). Moreover, physiological measures often

459 reveal minimal responses to predator odors (Wang et al., 2023; Zambra et al., 2021),
460 whereas the absence of conspecifics can lead to significant increases in cortisol and
461 catecholamine levels (Guesdon et al., 2012, 2015). These findings emphasize that the
462 lack of social resources appears to have a more pronounced effect than the presence
463 of predator cues alone, and, more generally, the need to carefully take attention of the
464 context in which the odors are diffused. This is why we have suggested to evaluate the
465 emotional valence of odors in presence of social resource (Achin et al. 2025).
466 Furthermore, our results did not reveal a strong positive emotional valence of orange.
467 In the positive context of our study, the availability of social and food resources may
468 make it difficult to observe a positive effect associated with orange. The increase in
469 feed intake described by Simitizis (2005) was not observed in our study because the
470 ewes in the control situation already ate their entire ration. At best, we might have
471 observed an effect in ewes interested in the social resource without eating in control
472 situation, but they were not motivated by the food resource in the presence of orange
473 either. Finally, we could have observed an effect of orange with ewes remaining close
474 to the odor source after finishing their ration, but the ewes seem to have been more
475 motivated to join their conspecifics once the food ration was finished. More generally,
476 this observation raises the question of the possibility of demonstrating the positive
477 emotional valence of an odor in an environment that is already perceived as positive.
478 Our results challenge the emotional valences of olfactory stimuli, reinforcing the idea
479 that animal behaviors result from a trade-off between social and food motivations.
480 These trade-offs involve balancing the need to seek food resources with the need for
481 vigilance against potential predation (Apfelbach et al., 2005). Our observations may
482 resemble what has been described in studies on animals exposed to parasite-infested

483 feces (Hutchings et al., 2000, 2017), where similar trade-offs between food-seeking
484 and risk assessment occur.

485 Our findings with wolf feces raise the question of whether olfaction alone is sufficient
486 to trigger an alert response, or if the activation of multiple sensory modalities is
487 necessary to detect a stronger effect. For instance, Kluever et al. (2009) demonstrated
488 that a combination of visual and olfactory cues from wolves leads to increased
489 vigilance, it does not alter their behavior towards a highly appetitive food resource. This
490 highlights the need for a multimodal approach when investigating predator-prey
491 interactions and suggests that odor alone may not always elicit the expected
492 behavioral responses in prey species.

493 To conclude, our experimental setup, which operates within a positive context, helps
494 limit stress during the presentation of olfactory stimuli. Indeed, the ewes exposed to 3g
495 or 15g of wolf feces did not express strong negative emotional responses, although a
496 repellent effect was observed. This may suggest that a positive context in the
497 experimental setup induces a reduction in their level of vigilance, compared to a
498 negative context. In the presence of orange essential oil, the expected positive
499 emotional valence was not clearly found, mainly in comparison with the control
500 situation. Can an odor induce a positive emotion outside of a negative context, thereby
501 demonstrating a calming effect? Ewes exposed to cadaverine did not exhibit behaviors
502 associated with a negative emotional valence, which raises questions about their ability
503 to identify the odor of death or carcasses, such as in abattoir settings. This suggests
504 that cadaverine, may not always evoke a strong negative emotional response, in
505 accordance with the findings of Pinel, Gorzalka, et al. 1981 and Hussain et al. 2013.

506 Furthermore, the personality of individuals plays an important role in their response to
507 odors. As suggested by Nielsen, the motivation and valence of the odor could jointly
508 account for the emotional response to olfactory stimuli, emphasizing the complex
509 interplay between individual traits and environmental factors in shaping animal
510 behavior (Nielsen et al. 2015).

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511 **Ethics approval**

512 The study was conducted in accordance with the European Directive 2010/63/EU on
513 the protection of animals used for scientific purposes and was approved by the local
514 animal ethics committee (CEEA VdL, Tours, France, authorization 2022-1511-1).

515 **Data and model availability statement**

516 The dataset used in this study is published in open-access
517 (<https://doi.org/10.57745/RNBPWR>). All analyses were conducted using open-source
518 and free software. No proprietary software was used in the study.

519 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing**
520 **process**

521 During the preparation of this work the authors used Chat GPT in order to translate
522 from French to English. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the
523 content and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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532 **Declaration of interest**

533 None

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666 **Abbreviations**

667 OS: Olfactory Stimulation

668 SR: Social Resource

669 FR: Food Resource

670 Lat: Latency

671 TS: Time Spent

672 Occ: Occurrence

673 PCA: Principal Component Analysis

674 LDA: Linear Discriminant Analysis

675 W: Water

676 O: Orange essential oil

677 WF: Wolf feces

678 C: Cadaverine

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679 **Table 1.** Organization of OS exposures for identifying emotional valences of predator
680 and orange.

	DAY 1	DAY 2	DAY 3	DAY 4
N = 15 ewes	Water 1.5 mL	Wolf feces 3 g	Orange essential oil 15 μ L	Water 1.5 mL
N = 15 ewes		Orange essential oil 15 μ L	Wolf feces 3 g	

681 Animals were exposed to water the day before and the day after OS-exposures. Half
682 of the ewes were exposed to wolf feces and then orange essential oil, while the other
683 half were first exposed to orange essential oil and then wolf feces. The first
684 experimentation occurred from the 23rd to the 26th of January 2023.

685 **Table 2.** Organization of OS exposures for identifying a gradient in the negative
686 emotional valences of predator and cadaverine.

	DAY 1	DAY 2	DAY 3	DAY 4
N = 12 ewes		Wolf feces 15 g	Water 1.5 mL	Cadaverine 1 mL
N = 9 ewes	Water 1.5 mL	Cadaverine 1 mL	Wolf feces 15 g	Water 1.5 mL
N = 9 ewes		Water 1.5 mL	Cadaverine 1 mL	Wolf feces 15 g

687 Animals were exposed to water the day before OS-exposures. The order of OS
688 exposure was randomized including predator, cadaverine and water (control situation).
689 The second experimentation occurred from the 13rd to the 16th of February 2023.

690 **Table 3** Table of Observed Behaviors and Corresponding Variables

Behavior	Description	Variables	Abbreviation
Head in the box	The animal is considered to have its head in the box when its snout is inside.	Latency	Box_Head_Lat
		Time Spent	Box_Head_TS
Head in the box without eating	The animal has its head in the box but is not eating.	Time Spent	Box_Head_No_Eat_TS
Muzzle against the wall of the box	The animal touches an internal wall of the box, the cotton pad or the round green plastic trough with its muzzle, without eating.	Occurrence	Box_Muzzle_Occ
		Time Spent	Box_Muzzle_TS
Eat in the trough	The animal eats in the trough.	Occurrence	Eat_Trough_Occ
		Time Spent	Eat_Trough_TS
Eat in the box	The animal eats inside the box.	Occurrence	Eat_Box_Occ
		Time Spent	Eat_Box_TS
First feeding	The first time the animal eats in the box.	Time Spent	Eat_First_TS
		Latency	Eat_First_Lat
Vocalizations	The animal emits vocalizations.	Latency	Voc_Lat
		Occurrence	Voc_Occ
Location	Three zones were delineated: near the social resource, in front of the test entrance, near the food resource. The individual is considered in a zone when its 2 front paws are in it. When the individual is positioned between two zones, its location is determined by the orientation of its muzzle.	Latency	Social_Zone_Lat Food_Zone_Lat
		Occurrence	Social_Zone_Occ Zone_Entrance_Occ Food_Zone_Occ
		Time Spent	Social_Zone_TS Food_Zone_TS
		Time Spent the first time	Social_Zone_First_TS Food_Zone_First_TS
			Zone_Crossed
Locomotion	Number of zones crossed.		
Urine	Presence of urine.	Occurrence	X_Urine
Feces	Presence of feces.	Occurrence	X_Feces

692 **Table 4:** Values of the variables contributing to the LDA (med [Q1-Q3]) and differences revealed by Friedman tests.

Variables	Water (W)	Orange essential oil (O)	Wolf feces (WF)	Friedman Test		Post-hoc comparisons
				χ^2	p-value	p-value
Box_Head_no_Eat_TS	21.8 s [13.6-30.2] s	17.1 s [9.2-26.8] s	8.2 s [5.1-14.5] s	7.3	0.02	W \neq WF, 0.02
Box_Head_TS	129.9 s [110.6-155] s	115.8 s [102.4-147.5] s	128.2 s [104.3-174.3] s	5.4	0.06	∅
Box_Muzzle_Occ	3 [2-7]	3 [1-5.5]	1 [0-2.5]	7.6	0.02	W \neq WF, 0.015
Eat_Though_TS	86.4 s [73.6-103.2] s	87.1 s [70-106.6] s	115.2 s [75.3-149.5] s	6.3	0.04	O \neq WF, 0.012
Eat_Total_TS	106 s [94.7-133.4] s	100.4 s [92.1-128.8] s	124.3 s [91.5-157] s	7.9	0.02	O \neq WF, 0.045
Food_intake	300 g [295-300] g	299.8 g [297-299.8] g	291 g [208-297] g	18	0.0001	W \neq WF, 0.008 O \neq WF, 0.0005
Food_Zone_No_Eat_TS	49 s [43.4-61.8] s	45.1 s [28.4-68.1] s	32.5 s [23.3-41.6] s	10.5	0.005	W \neq WF, 0.02 7
Food_Zone_Occ	6 [4.5-8]	5 [5-7]	5 [3-6]	10.2	0.006	W \neq WF, 0.012 O \neq WF, 0.022
Food_Zone_TS	167.7 s [147.6-190.7] s	148.7 s [132-169.1] s	159.2 s [127.2-211.1] s	3.7	0.1	∅
Social_Zone_Occ	8 [6-9.5]	8 [5.5-9]	7 [4-10]	0.07	0.9	∅
Social_Zone_TS	77.2 s [57.8-97.4] s	98 s [80.1-115] s	89.1 s [56.5-121.2] s	7.9	0.02	W \neq O, 0.02
Zone_Entrance_Occ	13 [11-17]	13 [11-16]	12 [8-16.5]	0.7	0.68	∅

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Table 5: Values of the variables contributing to the LDA (med [Q1-Q3]).

Variables	Water (W)	Cadaverine (C)	Wolf feces (WF)	Friedman Test		Post-hoc Comparisons
				χ^2	p-value	p-value
Box_Muzzle_TS	8.4 s [0-21.6] s	7.7 s [0-19.8] s	2.6 s [0-6.1] s	7.3	0.02	W \neq WF, 0.008 C \neq WF, 0.03
Eat_Though_Occ	8 s [6-9] s	7 s [4;10]	6 s [4;12]	0.2	0.9	∅
Food_Zone_First_TS	117.1 s [97.7-134.7] s	113.9 s [100.3-131.5] s	111.4 s [28.4;137.2] s	1.1	0.5	∅
Food_Zone_Lat	2.6 s [1-4.7] s	2.2 s [0.7-3.8] s	2.4 s [1-3.5] s	8	0.01	W \neq WF, 0.008
Zone_Entrance_Occ	9 [7-14]	8 [6-12]	8 [5-12]	3.8	0.1	∅

696

697 **Figure captions**

698 **Fig. 1.** Photograph of the experimental setup. Ewe 6 is being tested in the corridor.

699 Three zones were virtually delineated: on the right side the “food zone” closed to the
700 food resource (300 g of pellets in green plastic bucket placed in the PMMA box), on
701 the left the “social zone” closed to the companions’ pen, and on the middle the
702 “entrance zone”. During the test, the OS or the water impregnated-cotton pad was
703 placed behind the green bucket in the box (arrow).

704

705 **Fig. 2.** Individual profiles (N=28) of behaviors indicating a main interest for food
706 resource (eat, in blue) or for social resource (located in the zone near companions, in
707 purple) and an emotion-related behavior (vocalization, red dot). Based on these
708 behaviors, individuals were classified in three different classes of interest: social, food
709 and ambivalent. Star indicates the animals which ate their entire pellets ration.

710

711 **Fig. 3.** Individuals factor map of the PCA performed with all behaviors measured in
712 control situation (Exp1: n=28 ewes and Exp2: n=30 subjected four times to control
713 situation, water; 29 variables for calculating the components). Each water exposure is
714 symbolized by different colors.

715

716 **Fig. 4.** Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) result. **A.** Score plot where ellipses indicate
717 95% confidence interval of each exposure. **B.** Biplot of the variables that contribute in
718 the LDA axis for at least 75%. (LDA performed on 23 ewes and 29 variables).

719 **Fig. 5. A.** Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) result. **A.** Score plot where ellipses
720 indicate 95% confidence interval of each exposure. **B.** Biplot of the variables that

721 contribute in the LDA1 axis for at least 75%. (LDA performed on 29 ewes and 29
722 variables).

723

724 **Fig. 6.** Comparison of discriminant behaviors across Water (blue), Cadaverine
725 (purple), and Wolf Feces (red). **A.** Time spent with the muzzle in the box. **B.** Number
726 of occurrences of eating through the trough. **C.** Time spent the first time in the zone
727 near the food resource. **D.** Latency to enter the zone near the food resource. **E.**
728 Occurrence of entering the zone near the entrance. **F.** Food intake. A p-value below
729 0.05 is indicated by one asterisk (*). *If a p-value is below 0.01, it is indicated by two*
730 *asterisks (**). If a p-value is below 0.001, it is indicated by three asterisks (***)*